

Leveraging LLMs and Knowledge Graphs for Personalized Community Resource Recommendations in Healthcare

*Note: Sub-titles are not captured in Xplore and should not be used

1st Megan Tibbles

*Digital Healthcare Innovation Lab.
University of Guelph.
Guelph, Canada
mtibbles@uoguelph.ca
ORCID:0009-0004-6502-4940*

2nd Bamikole Adeawle

*Digital Healthcare Innovation Lab
Algoma University
Brampton, Canada
badewale@algomau.ca
ORCID:0009-0009-0169-9574*

3rd Mahreen Nasir

*School of Computer Science & Tech.
Algoma University
Saulte Ste. Marie, Canada
mahreen.nasir@algomau.ca
ORCID:0000-0002-5412-440X*

4th Teryn Bruni

*Department of Psychology
Algoma University
Saulte Ste. Marie, Canada
teryn.bruni@algomau.ca
ORCID:0000-0003-2359-4043*

5th Nikki Shaw

*Department of Biology
Algoma University
Saulte Ste. Marie, Canada
nikki.shaw@algomau.ca
ORCID:0000-0002-7936-0521*

6th Nirosha Murugan

*Department of Biology
Algoma University,
Saulte Ste. Marie, Canada
nmurugan@wlu.ca
ORCID:0000-0001-7260-9956*

7th Wenjun Lin*

*Digital Healthcare Innovation Lab
Algoma University
Brampton, Canada
randy.lin@algomau.ca
ORCID:0000-0002-3907-1995*

Abstract—Social determinants of health such as education, socioeconomic status and environmental conditions significantly influence a person’s well-being, yet these determinants are often difficult to address in clinical settings due to limited time and lack of comprehensive resource knowledge. This paper presents a personalized community resource recommendation system (CKGRS - (Community Knowledge Graph Recommendation Systems)) that leverages Large Language Models (LLMs) and Knowledge Graphs (KGs) to assist physicians in identifying community resources (medical and non-medical) tailored towards their patients’ needs.

CKGRS processes unstructured physician notes to extract relevant information, determines a patient’s key concerns, and recommends appropriate community resource categories. The system utilizes a knowledge graph derived from the Precision Medicine Knowledge Graph (PrimeKG) which supplements the LLM’s decision making by providing structured background knowledge.

Experiments were conducted on 58 human-created scenarios across 15 resource categories including Health and Medical Care, Allied Health Services, Caregiver Supports, Community Programs, Senior Support Services, and Transportation. CKGRS was compared to a baseline method and three alternative KG placements in the framework to assess performance in relevant keyword extraction and category recommendation.

Identify applicable funding agency here. If none, delete this.

Index Terms—Large Language Models, Computer Assisted Decision Making, Knowledge bases, community health services, referral and consultation

I. INTRODUCTION

Biological characteristics such as genetics and lifestyle choices like diet and exercise play a critical role in determining an individual’s well-being [1]. Non-medical factors like education, socioeconomic status and environmental conditions also have a large impact on one’s overall well-being. These are known as social determinants of health.

Despite their significant impact on an individual’s health, social determinants are often challenging to address within the constraints of a typical doctor’s visit. Physicians primarily focus on diagnosing and treating medical conditions, while factors such as housing insecurity, food access, and financial instability require specialized community-based resources. A study investigating the effects of social support programs for elderly individuals with depression found that these programs significantly reduced their symptoms [2].

To bridge this gap, we propose a way to increase access to these community resources (medical and non medical) by providing personalized recommendations to patients based on

doctor’s initial analysis notes. This paper aims to develop and evaluate such recommendation system, including the data used with the model. Our proposed CKGRS uses LLM’s coupled with a knowledge graph that is derived from the Precision Medicine Knowledge graph.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Current work on community resource recommendation systems focuses mainly on two key areas.

The first area involves the development and maintenance of comprehensive resource databases. The second area of focus pertains to the recommendation process itself, specifically how the system evaluates a patient’s needs and identifies the most appropriate resources.

Recommendation systems are commonly found in the medical field. There are many uses for this technology, such as matching patients to physicians, diseases, and treatments.

The following examples share the goal of matching patients to physicians through methods that do not use LLMs. Hanqi Wen et. al [3] proposed a novel method called adjust-exponential inventory balancing algorithm. It matches patients to physicians while considering the availability of these physicians, effectively incorporating a resource allocation perspective. One of the limitations of this method is the assumption that the patient will provide a specific disease type and that the number of disease types is finite.

A similar study [4] used the user’s preferences, which it extracts through web-mining, to find the physician that best matches those preferences. This study also considers the quality of the physicians by evaluating them before making recommendations. The system works by semantically aligning illness symptoms and user preferences with characteristics in a physician’s profile. This method differs from ours by not assessing the broad underlying problems and instead focuses on matching specific features. This narrow approach may result in the system prioritizing individual symptoms while missing the overall context.

A model created by Chunhua Ju and colleagues [5] which uses ontology characteristics and disease text mining to match patient symptoms to a specialist using word vectors and semantic similarity. Ontology characteristics refer to patients’ description texts and doctor’s specialties. One of the limitations of this study is its focus on symptoms, without accounting for other aspects of a patient’s life. Factors such as lifestyle, support network, and environmental conditions can significantly influence a patient’s needs. Overlooking these factors may limit the system’s ability to provide a complete recommendation.

The smart community health platform [6] proposed by Mehdi Mekni et. al. matches individuals with resources using a tool called MyStrengths MyHealth. This tool uses the Omaha System, which covers 42 concepts across four main areas: environments, psychosocial, physiological, and health-related behaviours. To build upon works similar to Omaha System, our system proposes the use of LLMs to help provide contextual information to enhance the systems system.

LLMs are a significant advancement due to their natural language processing, reasoning, summarization, and real-world knowledge capabilities. A recent study [7] used LLMs to retrieve and encode supporting information to improve the recommendation tasks. Similarly, work by Dario Di Palma [8] shows the ability of LLMs to improve recommender systems in situations where there was limited or unstructured data.

Studies using LLMs in medical recommendation systems demonstrate the possibility of applying AI to community resource recommendation. One study [9] used LLMs to analyze user provided medical text and then match symptoms to illnesses. This system used a model pre-trained on medical text to ensure domain-specific accuracy. Another study by Shishir Dwivedi et. al [10] uses an LLM-powered chatbot to process unstructured text inputs to recommend medical solutions. These examples show how LLMs can effectively process and analyze unstructured data, but in situations where domain-specific knowledge is required, they may lack critical information. The potential gap in knowledge can be supplemented in the form of knowledge graphs [7].

Knowledge graphs represent complex datasets. They consist of nodes and edges, the nodes are entities and the edges are the relationships between them. A survey on knowledge graph-based recommendation systems [11] dives into how knowledge graphs can be used with recommendation systems. This paper discusses three methods, the embedding-based method which uses the semantic relations, the connection-based method which focuses on the relationships more than the entities, and the propagation-based method which is a combination.

The embedding-based method is the most flexible of the three, making it work for most applications. It is also the least computationally complex, which makes it better with large datasets. However, the embedding method may lack the comprehensive understanding that the propagation-based method provides, as it focuses on the nodes instead of placing equal importance on the connections.

Another paper [12] explored using incomplete or noisy knowledge graphs with recommender systems. This paper found that these imperfect knowledge graphs can still be effective, this is important for real world applications because creating a perfect knowledge graph is impractical.

One of the main benefits of knowledge graphs is the ability to represent semantic relations [13]. This makes them work well with many AI systems such as question-answering systems, information retrieval tools, and recommender systems. By combining the LLMs ability to retrieve and encode information, with the knowledge graphs ability to represent semantic relationships, the recommender system gains a high-level understanding of the context and connections within data.

Yuqi Wang et. al [14] explores combining LLMs with knowledge graphs and discusses how these tools can work together. In their approach, the LLM executed the recommendation task and the knowledge graph provided background information. Their findings showed that integrating a knowledge graph improved the LLM’s recommendation performance compared

TABLE I
POSTPARTUM DEPRESSION INFORMATION

name	Description
Postpartum Depression	Depression in postpartum women, usually within four weeks after giving birth. The degree of depression ranges from mild transient depression to neurotic or psychotic depressive disorders.
	Symptoms
	Signs and symptoms of depression after childbirth vary, and they can range from mild to severe. Baby blues symptoms, Signs and symptoms of baby blues — which last only a few days to a week or two after your baby is born — may include: Mood swings, Anxiety, Sadness, Irritability, Feeling overwhelmed, Crying, Reduced concentration, Appetite problems, Trouble sleeping, Postpartum depression symptoms, Postpartum depression may be mistaken for baby blues at first — ...
	Causes
	here’s no single cause of postpartum depression, but physical and emotional issues may play a role. Physical changes. After childbirth, a dramatic drop in hormones in your body may contribute to postpartum depression. Other hormones produced by your thyroid gland also may drop sharply — which can leave you feeling tired, sluggish and depressed. Emotional issues.
	Risk Factors
	Any new mom can experience postpartum depression and it can develop after the birth of any child, not just the first. However, your risk increases if: You have a history of depression, either during pregnancy or at other times, You have bipolar disorder, You had postpartum depression after a previous pregnancy, You have family members who’ve had depression or other mood disorders. ...
	Complications
	Left untreated, postpartum depression can interfere with mother-child bonding and cause family problems. For mothers. Untreated postpartum depression can last for months or longer, sometimes becoming a chronic depressive disorder. Even when treated, postpartum depression increases a woman’s risk of future episodes of major depression. ...
When to See a Doctor	
When to see a doctor, If you’re feeling depressed after your baby’s birth, you may be reluctant or embarrassed to admit it. But if you experience any symptoms of postpartum baby blues or postpartum depression, call your doctor and schedule an appointment. If you have symptoms that suggest you may have postpartum psychosis, get help immediately. ...	

```

embedding [-0.0450047105550766,-0.00014262385957
408696,0.013108167797327042,0.06827171
14686966,-0.05172264575958252,0.001439
6796468645334,0.02820987068116665,0.0
... Show all]
name postpartum_depression

```

Fig. 3. Example of a node embedding from the postpartum depression disease knowledge graph.

postpartum depression disease node with its corresponding embedding.

Similarity between nodes can be measured using cosine similarity. This is the cosine angle between two vectors. This measurement allows us to identify nodes with similar meanings, even when phrased differently. For example, the node “sleeping troubles” should have a high similarity score to “difficulty sleeping”, as they both represent the same idea.

3) **Knowledge Graph Information Retrieval:** The purpose of the knowledge graph is to supply additional relevant information to the LLM. One of the challenges is choosing which information to use. The first step in this process is to identify keywords and phrases to search for, this step is outlined in the recommendation task section. Once we have a search term, it is embedded using the same method used to embed all nodes. The cosine similarity value between our search term and all existing nodes in the knowledge graph is then calculated. Matches with a score above the threshold value are returned. These returned nodes are treated as representations of our search term. The retrieved nodes provide valuable contextual information through their connections. A two step connection method involves retrieving the nodes from the initial search results, continued by a second round of connected nodes.

B. Recommendation Task

The recommendation part of the system is the process that runs each time a patient is analyzed and a recommendation is made. The process uses the knowledge graph that was built in the previous section to aid the LLM that is making the recommendation.

1) **Physician Note Analysis:** All the information we have on a patient is from a physician’s note. Our system aims to determine the most important information from this note by extracting the keywords and phrases that are most relevant. The purpose of this is to condense the detailed content of the physician’s note into concise points for the subsequent steps. Using an LLM to complete this task allows for the context to be taken into account.

Fig. 4 is an example of a physician’s note, where the highlighted lines in fig.4 indicate which part of the note the keywords come from. The following are some of the keywords extracted from the note: *Arthritis, Diabetes, Stroke, Difficulty with walking, etc...*

2) **Utilizing the Knowledge Graph and Determining the Main Problems:** Before identifying the main problems the patient is facing, our system retrieves relevant information from the knowledge graph to provide to the LLM. The process begins with a similarity search for all keywords and phrases extracted from a physician’s note. Once the similar nodes are found, a one step connection search is performed for each node. This results in the original keywords from the note being enhanced with related keywords, which may include symptoms, causes, risk factors, side effects, or related diseases.

For example, given the keyword “diabetes”, the knowledge graph might provide the following related keywords:

Senior Support Intake Scenario
General Information:

1. Full Name (as it appears on health card): Dennis Mennis
2. Date of Birth: January 16, 1951
3. Sex: Male
4. Phone number: 7057294839
5. Family Doctor/Nurse Practitioner (if applicable): Dr. McLean
6. Address: Sault Ste. Marie
7. Emergency Contact Name: Don Mennis
8. Emergency Contact Relationship: Son
9. Emergency Contact Phone Number: 7057394749

Health History:

1. Have you been diagnosed with any mental or physical health conditions?
 - Yes **Arthritis, Diabetes, Stroke**
2. Are you currently taking any medications or vitamins? (Please list names, dosages)
 - Yes, metformin
3. Do you have any allergies to medications, food, or other substances? (If yes, please provide details)
 - No
4. Do you have any significant family history or medical conditions?
 - **Diabetes**
5. Have you had any surgeries, hospitalizations, or significant injuries? (If yes, please provide details)
 - Stroke

Current Health Conditions:

1. What is the main reason for your virtual care appointment today?
 - I have been having a hard time taking care of myself and I am looking for home care services.
2. When did your symptoms or concerns first begin?
 - 6 months ago
3. Do you have any difficulties with activities of daily living? (Check all that apply)
 - Walking - Yes
 - Grooming - Yes
 - Dressing - Yes
 - Toileting - Yes
 - Eating/Taking Medications - Yes
 - Transferring from bed to chair - Yes
 - Other (Please provide details):
4. How would you rate the severity of your symptoms on a scale of 1 to 10? 10
5. Have you consulted a healthcare provider about this issue before? (If yes, please provide details) Yes. I see my doctor regularly and he has me on a waitlist for a PSW to come but I feel this is urgent.
6. Are you currently receiving services from any healthcare agencies? (If yes, please provide details) No

Safety and Accessibility:

1. Do you have any health insurance? Yes
2. Do you have any cultural or language preferences for your care? No

Fig. 4. Sample physician’s note containing information typically gathered during a clinical visit.

blurred vision, fatigue, increase thirst, frequent urination, extreme hunger, unexplained weight loss, irritability, slow-healing sores, gestational diabetes, obesity

With this additional set of keywords, the next step involves determining the patient’s primary problems. The physician’s note is provided as input to the LLM, along with the related keywords as background information. This supplemental knowledge bridges gaps between the LLM’s general real-world training and the specialized medical knowledge required for this task.

After determining the main problems, the system also identifies the keywords from the note associated with each problem and evaluates their severity. Severity scores represent the extent to which the patient is affected by each problem.

Here is an example of the main problems identified from the sample physician note: *Arthritis, Diabetes, Stroke, Difficulty walking, inability to perform self-care tasks*

For the problem “Diabetes”, the related keywords and their severity scores may look like the following: *Keywords: Diabetes: 10, Metformin: 8, Family history of diabetes: 7, Stroke: 8, Activities of daily living: 9, Home care services: 9, PSW: 8*

This process ensures a complete and prioritized understanding of the patient’s needs, resulting in more informed recommendations for resources.

3) **Final Recommendation:** The final step in this process is to use all the information gathered thus far to recommend appropriate resource categories for the patient. This step also uses an LLM, which takes the main problems, related keywords, and severity scores determined in the previous step as input. The output is 2 to 6 resource categories tailored to the patient’s needs.

The categories of resources are the following: addictions, allied health services, caregiver supports, community programs, developmental / behavioural supports, disabilities, domestic abuse / assault services, eating disorders, education, emergency / crisis, employment / training, family counselling, family services, financial assistance, food, francophones, government / legal, grief services, health / medical care, homelessness, housing / clothing, indigenous people, individual counselling, LGBTQ+, newcomers, parenting / child support, prenatal services, primary care / walk-in, senior support services, sports / recreation, transportation, trauma services, women and children support, youth services.

This list is a combination of resource topics from Ontario 211, a database of organizations and programs, as well as additional categories identified by the team. The goal was to capture a wide range of potential resources without being overly specific, ensuring broad capability.

IV. RESULTS

The research team created 55 unique scenarios spanning 15 topics, including mental health, addictions, medical care, food assistance, among others. These scenarios were designed to represent the large range of resource categories. Each scenario consisted of a physician’s note as input, alongside a set of keywords and resource categories to be recommended as output. Table II explains the different configurations in the proposed framework for experimental analysis.

We compared our proposed method to a baseline by establishing a process that followed the same steps, but without using the knowledge graph. This allowed us to assess the impact of supplemental information on the LLM’s performance. The baseline method involved the following steps:

- 1) Keyword extraction: Extract keywords from the physician’s input.
- 2) Problem identification: Identify five main issues using the extracted keywords.
- 3) Additional keyword extraction: Extract additional keywords based on the five main problems.
- 4) Resource recommendation: Choose 2 to 6 topics of resources that match the patient’s needs.

Note: All methods used OpenAi GPT-4o for the LLM.

Our proposed method (CKGRS) improves upon the baseline by integrating the knowledge graph between steps 1 and 2 as shown in fig.5. Specifically, keywords extracted from the input are used to search the knowledge graph for related information. This information is then incorporated in step 2 to enhance the identification of the main problems.

To further understand the effect of the knowledge graph, we tested three additional variations in the proposed framework.

TABLE II
COMPARISON AMONG VARIOUS CONFIGURATIONS FOR THE PROPOSED CKGRS

Strategy	Proposed Method	Baseline No KG	KG1	KG2	KG3
Extract keywords	✓*	✓	✓	✓	✓
Retrieve relevant information from KG	✓		✓ + 2*		✓
Identify 5 main problems	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Extract words related to main problems from KG.				✓	
Extract additional keywords based on main problems	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Choose 2-6 topics of resources that match the patient's needs	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

* Indicates that the strategy was implemented by the method.
+ 2 steps are additional connection and filtering.

Fig. 5. Comparison of the different processes carried out during the experiment.

- 1) **Extended knowledge graph search (KG1):** This method is similar to our proposed method but extends the search within the knowledge graph by performing a two-step connection. This information is then filtered by the LLM.
- 2) **Knowledge graph between steps 2 and 3 (KG2):** In this approach, the knowledge graph is used between steps 2 and 3. The knowledge graph is used after this step to provide additional context and refine the understanding of these problems.
- 3) **Dual knowledge graph use (KG3):** This method combines elements of both the proposed method and KG2, incorporating the knowledge graph twice. Once between steps 1 and 2, and again between steps 2 and 3 of the framework.

A. Keyword Evaluation

The first section we evaluated was the keyword extraction, which occurs in step 3 of our proposed method. The purpose of this evaluation was to discover if the system is identifying the most critical parts of the note. From this comparison, we calculated true positives, false positives, and false negatives. These values were used to compute accuracy, recall, precision, and F1 Score. Table III shows the F1 score for each resource category, the accuracy, recall and precision tables IX to XI can be found in the appendix.

Overall, both the proposed method and KG1 outperformed the baseline method across all evaluated categories. While KG1 showed advantages in some metrics such as accuracy and precision, our proposed method excelled in recall and F1 score. The baseline method, lacking the knowledge graph, consistently performed the worst.

TABLE III
MEAN - KEYWORD EVALUATION F1 SCORE

Category	Proposed Method	No KG Base-line	KG1	KG2	KG3
Mental Health	0.3874	0.2998	0.3653	0.3157	0.3547
Eating Disorders	0.3727	0.3668	0.3709	0.3468	0.3824
Medical Care	0.3209	0.2277	0.2646	0.1564	0.2875
"Abuse Assault and Domestic Violence"	0.3818	0.3264	0.3795	0.3524	0.3373
Disabilities	0.3707	0.3012	0.3644	0.1909	0.2338
Addictions	0.3646	0.3044	0.3791	0.2835	0.2835
Pregnancy	0.3666	0.2742	0.3934	0.3382	0.3204
Food Assistance	0.3534	0.2747	0.3425	0.3468	0.3165
Parenting-Children	0.3777	0.2066	0.4079	0.3271	0.2663
Caregiver Support	0.3548	0.2871	0.3589	0.3338	0.3338
Senior Support	0.3926	0.1333	0.4027	0.2315	0.2222
Financial + Legal Assistance	0.3892	0.2419	0.3792	0.3011	0.2802
Housing Needs - Clothing Needs	0.3791	0.2979	0.3857	0.3415	0.3054
LGBTQ2S+ Indigenous Support	0.3942	0.3207	0.3883	0.3366	0.3596
	0.3892	0.2809	0.3762	0.2752	0.2885

B. Resource Category Evaluation

The final stage of evaluation focuses on the recommendation of 2 to 6 resource topics tailored to the patient’s needs. This stage evaluates the system’s ability to accurately understand patient requirements and provide relevant resource suggestions.

For each scenario, the research team selected 2 to 6 appropriate topics, which were then compared to the system-generated recommendations. From this comparison, we determined true positives, false positives, true negatives, and false negatives. The values were then used to calculate accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. The mean evaluations of the F1 score can be seen in table IV, the accuracy, recall and precision tables VI to VIII can be found in the appendix.

TABLE IV
MEAN - CATEGORY RESOURCE EVALUATION F1 SCORE

Category	Proposed Method	No KG Base-line	KG1	KG2	KG3
Mental Health	0.3800	0.3400	0.3400	0.3400	0.3700
Eating Disorders	0.5800	0.5800	0.5700	0.6300	0.5500
Medical Care	0.3900	0.3800	0.3800	0.4100	0.4000
Disabilities	0.4900	0.4500	0.4100	0.4400	0.4000
Addictions	0.2300	0.2300	0.2300	0.2200	0.2300
Pregnancy	0.3300	0.3700	0.4200	0.4000	0.3200
Food Assistance	0.5300	0.5800	0.4400	0.5900	0.5900
Parenting-Children	0.3300	0.2800	0.2600	0.3000	0.3600
Caregiver Support	0.5500	0.4200	0.4100	0.4800	0.4300
Senior Support	0.6900	0.6400	0.5500	0.6700	0.6400
Financial + Legal Assistance	0.3900	0.3200	0.2200	0.3000	0.4000
Housing					
Needs-Clothing Needs	0.3100	0.3600	0.1700	0.3400	0.4300
LGBTQ2S+	0.3600	0.3500	0.3800	0.3700	0.3700
Indigenous Support	0.3200	0.2900	0.2700	0.3000	0.3100

To further assess the relevance of the recommendations, we compared the top human-selected resource category with the top three system-generated resource categories for each scenario V.

Overall, the proposed CKGRS emerged as the most robust strategy for resource topic recommendation, consistently outperforming other approaches across multiple categories.

V. DISCUSSION

The results from the keyword extraction task indicate that the proposed CKGRS and KG1 strategies were the most effective, outperforming all other methods. Both strategies use the knowledge graph between steps 1 and 2 of the framework, suggesting that this positioning yields the best results for keyword extraction. The performance of KG3, which used the KG in two positions, was weaker. This may indicate that introducing the knowledge graph at multiple points overcomplicates the process, potentially overwhelming the system or diminishing its effectiveness. Similarly, KG2, which places the

TABLE V
MEAN - MEAN RESOURCE CATEGORY EVALUATION TOP

Category	Proposed Method	No KG Base-line	KG1	KG2	KG3
Mental Health	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	0.9500	0.8600
Eating Disorders	0.9300	1.0000	0.8700	1.0000	0.8700
Medical Care	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	0.0000
Disabilities	0.5000	0.3300	0.5000	0.4200	0.4200
Addictions	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
Pregnancy	0.9200	0.8300	0.9200	0.8300	0.6700
Food Assistance	0.7500	0.7500	0.7500	0.8300	0.9200
Parenting-Children	0.5000	0.4200	0.4200	0.5000	0.5800
Caregiver Support	0.7500	0.5800	0.2500	0.5800	0.8300
Senior Support	0.8300	0.8300	0.5000	0.8300	0.8300
Financial + Legal Assistance	0.4200	0.4200	0.3300	0.5000	0.5000
Housing					
Needs-Clothing Needs	1.0000	0.9200	0.3300	0.9200	0.7500
LGBTQ2S+	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	0.6700
Indigenous Support	0.6700	0.6700	0.6700	0.6700	0.0000

KG between steps 2 and 3, performed poorly. This reinforces the idea that using the KG after the primary issues have been identified is less effective than incorporating it earlier in the process.

Overall, the proposed method is the most reliable and consistent approach. The placement of the knowledge graph between steps 1 and 2 proves to be the most effective configuration for both tasks. This suggests providing the LLM with supplemental information early in the decision making process is helpful. However, there seems to be a limit in the amount of information that is beneficial.

Despite inherent variability across different category scenarios, the proposed method maintains consistent performance. This confirms its effectiveness as an optimal strategy for using knowledge graphs in resource category recommendation.

One of the primary objectives of this paper was to assess whether the information from the original Precision Medicine Knowledge Graph (PrimeKG) could be used for our purposes. As a lack of data is one of the obstacles in this task, we wanted to see if we could transfer knowledge from one domain and utilize it for another. The results indicate that the knowledge graph was indeed helpful in multiple categories. Notably, our proposed method and KG1 performed well in categories such as parenting-children and financial and legal assistance, which are not directly aligned with the core focus of the PrimeKG. This suggests that the knowledge graph can still provide valuable insights even in domains outside its primary scope.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced a personalized community resource recommendation system that utilizes LLMs (LLMs) and knowledge graphs (KGs) to address both medical and non-medical determinants of health. Given that social factors such as housing, employment, financial stability, and social

support significantly impact health outcomes, an overreaching approach is necessary to ensure that patients receive the right support beyond clinical care.

While the current approach identifies relevant resource categories, the next logical step is to recommend specific, real-world resources within each category. This would involve integrating resource databases and refining the recommendation process to ensure that patients receive actionable and locally relevant support options.

Additionally, accessibility and patient preferences could be incorporated to improve the personalization of recommendations. In our sample physician notes, we included some formats with explicit questions about accessibility needs and personal preferences. Future versions of this system could use this information to filter the recommended resources based on factors such as location, cost, eligibility criteria, and language availability.

REFERENCES

- [1] E. Orille, M. B. Steck, and G. D. Brannan, "Determinants of health," in *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing, 2024.
- [2] S. H. Lee, H. Lee, and S. Yu, "Effectiveness of social support for community-dwelling elderly with depression: A systematic review and meta-analysis," in *Healthcare*, vol. 10. MDPI, 2022, p. 1598.
- [3] H. Wen, J. Song, and X. Pan, "Physician recommendation on healthcare appointment platforms considering patient choice," *IEEE Transactions on Automation Science and Engineering*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 886–899, 2020.
- [4] H. Jiang and W. Xu, "How to find your appropriate doctor: An integrated recommendation framework in big data context," in *2014 IEEE Symposium on Computational Intelligence in Healthcare and e-health (CICARE)*, 2014, pp. 154–158.
- [5] C. Ju and S. Zhang, "Doctor recommendation model based on ontology characteristics and disease text mining perspective," *BioMed Research International*, vol. 2021, no. 1, p. 7431199, 2021.
- [6] M. Mekni and D. Haynes, "Smart community health: a comprehensive community resource recommendation platform," in *Biomedical engineering systems and technologies, international joint conference, BIOSTEC... revised selected papers. BIOSTEC (Conference)*, vol. 5. NIH Public Access, 2020, p. 614.
- [7] Y. Xi, W. Liu, J. Lin, X. Cai, H. Zhu, J. Zhu, B. Chen, R. Tang, W. Zhang, and Y. Yu, "Towards open-world recommendation with knowledge augmentation from large language models," in *Proceedings of the 18th ACM Conference on Recommender Systems*, 2024, pp. 12–22.
- [8] D. Di Palma, "Retrieval-augmented recommender system: Enhancing recommender systems with large language models," in *Proceedings of the 17th ACM Conference on Recommender Systems*, ser. RecSys '23. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2023, p. 1369–1373. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3604915.3608889>
- [9] S. L. Adu and S. Srijayanthi, "Integrated ai-driven healthcare system: Predictive diagnosis, personalized medical-report content generation, and physician recommendation," in *2024 2nd International Conference on Sustainable Computing and Smart Systems (ICSCSS)*, 2024, pp. 1148–1153.
- [10] S. Dwivedi, N. Srivastava, V. Rawal, and D. Dev, "Healpal chatmate: Ai driven disease diagnosis and recommendation system," in *2024 2nd International Conference on Disruptive Technologies (ICDT)*, 2024, pp. 1404–1408.
- [11] Q. Guo, F. Zhuang, C. Qin, H. Zhu, X. Xie, H. Xiong, and Q. He, "A survey on knowledge graph-based recommender systems," *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, vol. 34, no. 8, pp. 3549–3568, 2022.
- [12] Y. Yang, C. Huang, L. Xia, and C. Li, "Knowledge graph contrastive learning for recommendation," in *Proceedings of the 45th International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval*, ser. SIGIR '22. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2022, p. 1434–1443. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3477495.3532009>
- [13] C. Peng, F. Xia, M. Naseriparsa, and F. Osborne, "Knowledge graphs: Opportunities and challenges," *Artificial Intelligence Review*, vol. 56, no. 11, pp. 13 071–13 102, 2023.
- [14] B. Jiang, Y. Wang, Y. Luo, D. He, P. Cheng, and L. Gao, "Reasoning on efficient knowledge paths: knowledge graph guides large language model for domain question answering," in *2024 IEEE International Conference on Knowledge Graph (ICKG)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 142–149.
- [15] P. Chandak, K. Huang, and M. Zitnik, "Building a knowledge graph to enable precision medicine," *Scientific Data*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 67, 2023.

APPENDIX

TABLE VI
MEAN - CATEGORY RESOURCE EVALUATION ACCURACY

Category	Proposed Method	No KG Base-line	KG1	KG2	KG3
Mental Health	0.8800	0.8700	0.8600	0.8600	0.8700
Eating Disorders	0.8900	0.8900	0.8900	0.9000	0.8800
Medical Care	0.8800	0.8800	0.8800	0.8900	0.8800
Disabilities	0.8700	0.8500	0.8500	0.8500	0.8400
Addictions	0.8300	0.8300	0.8400	0.8300	0.8300
Pregnancy	0.8500	0.8500	0.8600	0.8600	0.8400
Food Assistance	0.8900	0.9100	0.8800	0.9000	0.9100
Parenting-Children	0.8500	0.8400	0.8400	0.8400	0.8600
Caregiver Support	0.9000	0.8600	0.8600	0.8700	0.8700
Senior Support	0.9200	0.9100	0.8900	0.9200	0.9100
Financial + Legal Assistance	0.8700	0.8500	0.8300	0.8500	0.8700
Housing Needs-Clothing	0.8100	0.8300	0.7800	0.8200	0.8600
LGBTQ2S+ Indigenous Support	0.8400	0.8400	0.8500	0.8500	0.8500
Indigenous Support	0.8500	0.8400	0.8200	0.8400	0.8400

TABLE VII
MEAN - CATEGORY RESOURCE EVALUATION RECALL

Category	Proposed Method	No KG Base-line	KG1	KG2	KG3
Mental Health	0.7600	0.7100	0.7300	0.7500	0.7700
Eating Disorders	0.6500	0.6300	0.6300	0.7100	0.6300
Medical Care	0.7300	0.6800	0.7300	0.7300	0.7100
Disabilities	0.5700	0.5200	0.4700	0.5200	0.4300
Addictions	0.3000	0.3000	0.3000	0.3000	0.3000
Pregnancy	0.4600	0.5400	0.6000	0.5800	0.4400
Food Assistance	0.6600	0.7400	0.5300	0.7600	0.7600
Parenting-Children	0.4200	0.3500	0.3300	0.3800	0.4400
Caregiver Support	0.6000	0.4500	0.4500	0.5300	0.4700
Senior Support	0.7700	0.7300	0.5900	0.7400	0.7000
Financial + Legal Assistance	0.4900	0.4500	0.2600	0.3700	0.5100
Housing Needs-Clothing	0.3300	0.3800	0.1600	0.3600	0.4400
LGBTQ2S+ Indigenous Support	0.4800	0.4600	0.4900	0.4800	0.4800
Indigenous Support	0.4000	0.3800	0.3600	0.3800	0.4000

TABLE VIII
MEAN - CATEGORY RESOURCE EVALUATION PRECISION

Category	Proposed Method	No KG Base-line	KG1	KG2	KG3
Mental Health	0.2800	0.2500	0.2400	0.2500	0.2700
Eating Disorders	0.5300	0.5500	0.5300	0.5700	0.5000
Medical Care	0.2800	0.2900	0.2900	0.3100	0.3000
Disabilities	0.4300	0.4100	0.3800	0.3900	0.3800
Addictions	0.2000	0.2000	0.2100	0.1900	0.2000
Pregnancy	0.2600	0.3000	0.3300	0.3200	0.2600
Food Assistance	0.4500	0.4900	0.3900	0.5000	0.5000
Parenting-Children	0.2800	0.2400	0.2200	0.2600	0.3100
Caregiver Support	0.5100	0.4000	0.3800	0.4400	0.4000
Senior Support	0.6400	0.5900	0.5200	0.6200	0.6000
Financial + Legal Assistance	0.3400	0.2700	0.2000	0.2600	0.3400
Housing Needs-Clothing	0.3000	0.3600	0.1700	0.3300	0.4200
LGBTQ2S+ Indigenous Support	0.3000	0.3000	0.3100	0.3200	0.3100
Indigenous Support	0.2800	0.2400	0.2100	0.2500	0.2600

TABLE IX
MEAN - KEYWORD EVALUATION ACCURACY

Category	Proposed Method	No KG Base-line	KG1	KG2	KG3
Mental Health	0.6900	0.4900	0.6400	0.5200	0.5800
Eating Disorders	0.6000	0.5900	0.6100	0.5400	0.6500
Medical Care	0.5400	0.4100	0.5000	0.2400	0.4900
Disabilities	0.6700	0.5200	0.6600	0.3100	0.3700
Addictions	0.6200	0.4900	0.6500	0.4500	0.4400
Pregnancy	0.5800	0.4300	0.6700	0.5500	0.5000
Food Assistance	0.5700	0.4900	0.5600	0.5500	0.5100
Parenting-Children	0.6200	0.3400	0.7100	0.5300	0.4400
Caregiver Support	0.5700	0.4800	0.5700	0.5400	0.5400
Senior Support	0.6700	0.2200	0.6800	0.3800	0.3300
Financial + Legal Assistance	0.6800	0.4500	0.6400	0.4900	0.4800
Housing Needs-Clothing	0.6300	0.4600	0.6600	0.5600	0.4900
LGBTQ2S+ Indigenous Support	0.6600	0.5000	0.6600	0.5400	0.6100
Indigenous Support	0.6500	0.4700	0.6600	0.4100	0.4700

TABLE X
MEAN - KEYWORD EVALUATION RECALL

Category	Proposed Method	No KG Base-line	KG1	KG2	KG3
Mental Health	0.8667	0.6295	0.8055	0.7309	0.7661
Eating Disorders	0.8103	0.7583	0.7758	0.6857	0.7616
Medical Care	0.7076	0.5133	0.6465	0.4278	0.5887
Disabilities	0.8897	0.6253	0.7739	0.4315	0.4194
Addictions	0.7853	0.5824	0.7889	0.5386	0.5197
Pregnancy	0.8137	0.4931	0.8052	0.6954	0.6083
Food Assistance	0.8023	0.5862	0.7183	0.7168	0.6116
Parenting-Children	0.8289	0.3839	0.8873	0.6432	0.5456
Caregiver Support	0.7388	0.5136	0.7317	0.6176	0.6847
Senior Support	0.9167	0.2222	0.8667	0.5000	0.4222
Financial + Legal Assistance	0.8345	0.5208	0.7920	0.5552	0.5639
Housing Needs - Clothing Needs	0.7433	0.5668	0.7470	0.6848	0.6154
LGBTQ2S+	0.8173	0.6095	0.7946	0.6071	0.6385
Indigenous Support	0.7804	0.5071	0.6892	0.4908	0.4946

TABLE XI
MEAN - KEYWORD EVALUATION PRECISION

Category	Proposed Method	No KG Base-line	KG1	KG2	KG3
Mental Health	0.7428	0.6226	0.6975	0.5861	0.7104
Eating Disorders	0.6974	0.7398	0.7278	0.7103	0.7812
Medical Care	0.6265	0.4289	0.5883	0.3214	0.5817
Disabilities	0.6650	0.6579	0.7290	0.4175	0.5972
Addictions	0.6940	0.7003	0.7393	0.6183	0.6436
Pregnancy	0.6737	0.6375	0.7819	0.6804	0.6986
Food Assistance	0.6482	0.5979	0.6940	0.7222	0.7367
Parenting-Children	0.7082	0.4710	0.7745	0.6984	0.5464
Caregiver Support	0.7119	0.6892	0.7178	0.7827	0.6878
Senior Support	0.6889	0.3333	0.7556	0.4333	0.4722
Financial + Legal Assistance	0.7643	0.4667	0.7441	0.6831	0.5833
Housing Needs-Clothing Needs	0.8126	0.7478	0.8212	0.7193	0.6675
LGBTQ2S+	0.7843	0.7568	0.7856	0.8410	0.9086
Indigenous Support	0.8244	0.7213	0.8607	0.6747	0.7282